

Value chain Context diagnoses Deliverable 2.1

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Executive Summary

Introduction

The purpose of this report is to provide a diagnosis of the current situation of the MRT crops in those places where the ROTATES project happens, focusing on aspects related to the economic, social and cultural barriers to and enablers of the uptake of MRTs at value chain level and concerning all the cases for the 10 countries involved in the project.

It should be noted that the main aim of the report is to provide a background of all the aspects that will be important to consider in the next steps of Workpackage 2 - Value chain development for adoption and new market opportunities, where the specific value chains are going to be studied and where the aforementioned barriers and enablers will be studied in detail. It is also hoped that the material collected will also be useful to other partners in the project.

The work carried out has been a desk-based study collecting secondary information of the current situation of the MRTs at value chain level. This has been done considering the supply side (e.g., production, imports) and consumer side (or utilisation in the case of feed). This is because the report wants to highlight the challenges of expanding MRTs, why this needs to be done in a value chain context (i.e., there is the need to build or expand the sequence of productive activities for those crops that go from farmers to their final customers being these consumers or animal producers). Some of the aspects are not only whether the crop is currently produced and, in the country, but also its consumption. In case the crop is not produced or used, then it is crucial to highlight what crop is currently used as the potential introduction of the MRT is going to erode.

Methodology

Focusing on the four crops studied on the project (i.e., cassava, sweet potato, taro and yam) information was searched in online databases considering the cases of food and feed and for their respective countries. In all cases, the focus when compiling the evidence was to consider the entire value chains.

In terms of the aims of the report, it was to collect evidence about the crops' supply (i.e., domestic production and imports) and in particular their challenges and opportunities for expansion. In several cases (e.g., cassava made pasta or feed) where information for a particular country was limited it was expanded by considering evidence produced outside Europe. This helped identifying any limitation that may affect the supply.

In addition, information was searched considering the keywords "consumer response" and "consumer acceptance" to find articles focusing on the consumer response or interest regarding the MRT crops. Some of these, as in the case of pasta, were related to low in gluten or free, lactose-free. Another search related to consumers was about their preference for organic products and in the case.

For the feed cases, information was provided by the ROTATES partners, who described the current use of the MRT crops for feed and the feeding practices. They also indicated the probability of uptake under the current circumstances.

The qualitative information compiled from the literature review was complemented by quantitative information from FAOSTAT, Eurostat, CyStat (Cyprus Statistical Office) and COMTRADE (United Nations Commodity Trade database). The main purpose of this was to establish whether any trend was present, e.g., on areas dedicated to organic crops. To provide information about consumers' interest for food products with specific attributes such as organics, data about the evolution of the number of launched products with those attributes were accessed from Mintel's Global New Product Database (GNPD). The logic behind this was that food firms invest on new products with particular attributes when they identify that consumers would be interested in products with a particular attribute e.g., gluten free pasta (see Fuller, 2004; Lucas et al., 2021).

To compare the different cases and extract conclusions, a SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) analysis was used.

Project cases

Cyprus - Conventional taro (food)

The supply of taro is made almost exclusively by domestic production; a minor part of it is exported and imports are negligible. Data indicates that production has been steadily decreasing. Taro has a high demand of water and also requires fertiliser to improve soil texture and fertility during the growing season. Cultivation can be affected by serious pests and diseases infestations.

Taro is very much appreciated by consumers in Cyprus and widely used in the local cuisine. Nevertheless, per capita consumption of taro does not show a growing trend. This is despite that Taro has many health benefits.

France - Organic sweet potato (food)

The supply of sweet potatoes in France depends on imports. Information about the domestic production of sweet potatoes in France is scarce with some reports indicating that it has grown from 10,000 tonnes in 2018 to 24,000 tonnes in 2024 with some farms transitioning to more industrial-scale (organic and conventional), and organic cultivation. It is considered a difficult, labour-intensive crop, often requiring manual or mechanical weed control. Production faces challenges such as weather variability (heavy rains) and the need to manage pests.

There is a growing interest from French consumers in sweet potatoes. In recent years, the crop has gained in popularity due to its nutritional qualities as sweet potatoes are rich in beta-carotene, vitamin A, fibre and antioxidants. In addition, sweet potatoes also provide an opportunity for consumers to diversify their diets something that is reflected in the increasing number of recipes. The share of products with the organic attribute have shown a slow decrease since around the onset of the pandemic, which may indicate consumers are only modestly interested in products with that attribute.

Greece - Organic sweet potato (food)

Greece's Mediterranean climate makes growing tropical root vegetables like sweet potatoes a challenge. Nevertheless, some areas of Greece can support sweet potato cultivation on a small scale during the hot summer months. Yields show an increasing trend since the late 1990s whilst the area planted has remained stable although with high variability. The result is a stagnant and variable production.

The crop is favoured for being relatively low maintenance, though it requires significant water during the summer. Key challenges include high production costs, the potential for crop losses due to pests (worms) in wet years, and ensuring consistent, high-quality yields. The industry is seeing a shift toward more professionalised farming to boost export volumes, with a growing focus on organic production to meet European demand.

Growers face competition from cheaper Egyptian imports. Exports are increasing to countries like Germany, Spain, and Cyprus, which show rising demand. Since 2008, imports have consistently exceeded exports.

Greek consumers enjoy sweet potatoes baked, mashed, fried into fritters or chips, included in casseroles, pureed into soups, and used in desserts. However, culturally, sweet potatoes have not become truly mainstream in Greek cooking and are treated as more of a novelty ingredient. In general, there is no clear trend in the evolution of the share of products with the organic attribute, which remains under 15 per cent.

Guadeloupe - Conventional yam bread (food)

Although a traditional crop in Guadeloupe, in 2024 yam represented only 0.6 per cent of the total agricultural surface of the island. Local yams cover about 78 per cent of Guadeloupe's demand and the gap between local production and consumption is covered by imports. The production and cultivated area have decreased significantly over time.

The yam sector in Guadeloupe suffers from the following problems: (i) heavy constraints on production, primarily due to pests and high production costs and (ii) poor sector organisation.

Production and consumption of yam on the island were highly impacted by the discovery of long-lasting soil pollution associated with banana production. Lack of traceability and the presence of an informal market have contributed to the stagnation of the product.

Despite the existence of many varieties of yam, consumers are unaware of their differences, and this can provide a possibility for a marketing campaign that can expand the demand and create greater value for producers.

There is little information about the supply of yam bread. However, as yam bread requires fresh yams all the problems associated to yam production also affect yam bread.

Italy - Conventional pasta from an MRT (food)

The alternative pasta segment in Italy is expected to continue gradual growth, driven by health-conscious consumers and innovation in plant-based and gluten-free products. While still a minority compared to traditional wheat pasta, its market share is projected to increase steadily over the next decade.

While wheat-based pasta still dominates with about 91.8 per cent share, alternative pasta collectively accounts for roughly 8–9 per cent of the market, reflecting a gradual but steady shift toward healthier and specialty options. In fact, studies indicate that there is an increasing demand for innovative pasta products which is encouraging research on novel raw and processed materials to meet the consumer demand in terms of nutritional, sensory and technological value of pasta. It is important to note that major challenges for pasta industry are now to increase food healthiness but keeping high sensory attributes and cooking performances.

Portugal - Organic sweet potato (food)

The area under sweet potatoes in Portugal shows an important degree of variability, in general, fluctuating between 100 to 300 hectares. Since the late 1990s the production has remained stable at relatively low levels, with production around 15 to 20 thousand tonnes as of 2012-2023. Yields remained stable until the late 2000s after which they increased significantly with respect to its previous values. Since mid-2010s exports and imports started to show a significantly increasing trend (before that period the product was only sold domestically). In particular, exports have shown a remarkable increase since then. Portuguese producers face challenges with storage, packaging, and increasing production costs, often storing products to wait for better prices.

In Portugal, sweet potato is used for fresh but most production is processed after cutting and freezing (for dehydrate/desiccate for starch and baby food). Sweet potatoes can be consumed in various ways. The most traditional is boiled, with or without seasonings, as a substitute for other starchy crops (e.g., potatoes). Information indicates that Portuguese consumers have interest on organic fruit and vegetables.

Azores Island – Conventional taro (feed)

Taro is rich in essential nutrients like carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins, and minerals, supporting animal growth and health. Its medicinal properties, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory effects, offer potential benefits in disease management and animal welfare. By incorporating taro into animal diets and

utilising its medicinal properties, stakeholders can optimize animal performance, reduce disease risks, and contribute to overall animal well-being.

Taro is not currently used as animal feed in the Azores, at least not in a systematic or documented way. There is currently a scarcity of taro tubers for human consumption, which makes their use in animal feeding unlikely and economically unjustifiable. However, there may be potential interest in the medium to long term regarding taro leaves, which represent an agricultural residue.

The target species for the work are cattle (bovines), particularly within the Azorean livestock production systems. Currently, cattle feeding in the Azores is mainly based on pasture (fresh grass), complemented with conserved forages (silage and hay) and commercial concentrates, depending on the production system and season.

Potential advantages of the use of taro for feed include the valorisation of local agricultural residues and a reduced dependence on imported feed. Challenges include limited availability, lack of tradition and technical knowledge, the presence of antinutritional compounds, and competition with human food uses (except if only the leaves are used).

Canary Islands – Conventional cassava (feed)

Cassava has not yet been established in the Canary Islands as a commercial crop for human consumption, so it is not possible to use the by-products for animal feed. Within the project, the purpose is to focus specifically on small ruminants, including goats and poultry (including laying hens and broiler chickens). More generally, the results obtained could also be extrapolated to other ruminants such as cows, and sheep, and even later, once the relevant experiments have been carried out to other monogastric animals such as swine.

In the Canary Islands, animal feed is based on cereals (corn, oats, barley) and legumes (beans, peas, soybeans), all of which are imported, as local production is negligible. These grains are processed and formulated in different proportions in feed industries for subsequent sale and distribution to livestock farms. For ruminants, fodder or forage, such as lucerne, ryegrass, or cereal straw is also imported as fibrous feed.

Although there are farmers interested in growing it, the demand is still very low, and it is practically impossible to find plant material for cultivation. All the cassava present in the islands and used for food is imported.

Congo – Conventional cassava (feed)

Cassava is primarily used for human consumption (it is the staple food) in Congo. However, its use in livestock farming is growing as an economic alternative to replace maize, which is often expensive or imported.

Cassava peels from a traditional dish are immediately collected to serve as basic feed for pigs, goats, and sheep. In addition, surplus cassava leaves are used for small ruminants (sheep and goats). In some more structured farming operations, leaf ensilage is practiced preserving nutrient-rich fodder during the dry season. Also, retting water and small debris from the production of cassava paste are sometimes recovered, especially in rural areas, to water or feed pigs in a traditional manner.

French Guiana – Conventional cassava (feed)

Cassava is a common crop in French Guiana. Most of the farmers already have a few plants at home or around their homes. Feeding livestock is a very significant cost for farmers.

The use of cassava in animal feed is not extended in French Guiana and only few farmers use it mainly for chickens, ducks and pigs. Most of the animal feed relies on imports from mainland France. Regarding cattle farming, the systems are mostly extensive, but there are complementary inputs with fodder where cassava could be used.

SWOT Analysis

An analysis considering the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) was carried out for all the cases. The purpose was to classify the information collected section in the aforementioned categories to highlight aspects that need to be considered in the next phase of the value chain work in Workpackage 2.

Although all the four crops from the project are considered minor crops they have significant differences in terms of their situation in the studied places. For instance, the two crops considered for food in this study (i.e., taro and sweet potatoes) are well known in the countries of study by both producers and consumers. However, the demand of taro for food in Cyprus is stagnated. In contrast, the demand for sweet potatoes is rising domestically (e.g., in France where there is growing interest due to its nutritional characteristics). Although the domestic demand for sweet potatoes in Portugal and Greece is stable (i.e., not growing), the countries' producers benefit of an increasing foreign demand raising their exports.

It is important to note that in the case of sweet potatoes, ROTATES indicates organics as the production practice. Whilst the European Union is interested in expanding the organic supply, it needs to be done in parallel with consumers interest in organic product. The evidence about consumers interest on organic products is mixed (pointing out on the heterogeneity on consumers' preferences) and depends on factors such as prices and consumers' views about aspects such as nutrition and environment.

As regards processed products such as pasta from MRTs and yam bread an analysis of consumers preferences as their uptake will depend on factors such as their views of food safety, nutrition as well as flavours.

Increasing production costs are an issue in most of the studied cases. This is important because indicates the need to study the profitability of the crops with respects to alternative ones that may have higher profitability margins or less demand for some natural resources like water (e.g., taro in Cyprus or sweet potato in Greece).

Something that is common to most of the cases (food and feed) -the exception is taro for food in Cyprus- is the presence of imports, which either compete with the domestic production (e.g., organic sweet potatoes for food) or they are the mark that potential domestic feed from cassava or taro need to meet before being adopted by producers and customers.

Introduction

The 'Minor Roots and Tubers Fostering Agrobiodiversity and Ecosystem Services' (ROTATES) project aims to sustainably enhance agrobiodiversity and ecosystem services, i.e., the various benefits that humans derive from ecosystems, by introducing and promoting starchy root and tuber crops, considered minor and currently underutilised in Europe. The crops considered for improvement in the project are sweet potato, cassava, taro and yam (hereafter MRTs).

It is important to note that the overall objectives of ROTATES are to enhance the resilience of European agrosystems in a context of climate change, to reduce the negative impacts of agrosystems on the environment, and to respond to increased consumer demand for healthy food. To achieve this objective, it is imperative for producers to include these MRTs into their production activities.

The purpose of this report is to provide a diagnosis of the current situation of the MRT crops in the regions where the ROTATES project operates, focusing on the economic, social and cultural barriers to, and enablers of, the uptake of MRTs at value chain level, covering all 10 countries involved in the proposal.

The work carried out has been a desk-based study collecting secondary data on the economic, social and cultural barriers to, and enablers of, the uptake of MRTs at the value chain level. In addition, this report highlights the challenges of expanding MRTs, explains why this needs to be done within a value chain context (i.e., there is a need to build or expand the sequence of productive activities for these crops, from farmers to their final customers, whether these are consumers or animal producers).

In addition, the diagnosis included all aspects that will be important to consider in the next step of the project, where the specific value chains will be studied. Some aspects consider not only whether the crop is currently produced in the country, but also its consumption. If the crop is not produced or used, it is crucial to highlight which crop currently serves that purpose, as the potential introduction of the MRT could replace it.

It should be noted that the information used for the diagnosis was varied and depended on the data available for each of the countries in the project. It has been complemented with observations provided by the project's partners.

This report starts with an overview of the situation of the MRTs in the European Union, using the most recent statistical information from the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) for the period 2010 to 2023, and comparing it with potatoes, as they are the major tuber crop in Europe. Next the challenges are explained following with conclusions indicating the work ahead. Then, a brief methodology section is presented followed by the cases considered by the project, broken down first by those targeting food and feed, and then by country. The next section compares the different cases by using a strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) analysis. Finally, the last section presents the next steps of the research.

Situation of MRTs in the EU 27

The FAO data relate to the aggregated demand and supply of MRTs in the 27 member states of the European Union (i.e., EU 27). The aggregated demand is made of the uses for food, non-food and exports, whilst the aggregated supply is mainly comprised by domestic production and imports.

Figure 1 shows the differences in the aggregated demand for potatoes (the main tuber crop in the EU 27) and all the MRTs together. If one considers the average for the period, the demand for potatoes is about 141 times the one for MRTs. Another, aspect to highlight is that while the demand for potatoes is relatively stable during the period, the MRTs one shows mostly an increasing trend.

Figure 1: Aggregated demand for MRTs and potatoes

Source: FAOSTAT.

As mentioned, the MRTs aggregated demand is made of several components. The shares of these components are shown in Figure 2. Since 2015 the non-food (e.g., feed) and exports components are the most important uses of MRTs. In contrast, the food component shows a decreasing trend. This is also observed when the MRTs quantities for food are considered. This indicates that the MRTs are not currently fulfilling any role in terms of satisfying the demand for healthy food and they may be considered a new market opportunity for European countries.

Figure 2: Distribution of the MRTs aggregated demand

Source: FAOSTAT.

It is also important to highlight that the most important component, exports, represent about 50 per cent of the total utilisation of MRTs in the EU 27. This shows that most of the MRTs that are produced or imported by EU 27 leave the region (i.e., exported). This contrasts with potatoes where on average 31 per cent of the total aggregated supply is exported.

Finally, Figure 3 shows that an increasing proportion of the MRTs aggregated supply is made of imports and therefore domestic production is minimal. Whilst combining this information with Figure 2’s composition of the aggregated, it means that part of this supply is re-exported.

Figure 3: Imports' share of the total MRTs aggregated demand

Source: FAOSTAT.

Whilst there might be deficiencies on the data given the small presence of the MRTs in EU 27, the available data point out that there is significant work to do in terms of establishing or expanding those crops in EU 27. Also important is the need to make them known or appealed to consumers if they are to satisfy their demand for healthy products.

Challenges on building value chains for MRTs

The first step for fostering or building an increasing presence of MRTs is to understand why the MRTs did not receive enough attention as the case of mainstream crops (e.g., wheat, maize, rice). ROTATES adheres at the views from the CROPDIVA project that certain historical events led to the choice of some particular mainstream crops and they are developed in detriment with other crops (minor ones). The implications of this position can be explained by the diagram in Figure 4.

The starting point of Figure 4 is that at some point in history there was a lock in on the choice of MRTs crops. This means that they were relegated from being the focus of research that mainstream crops were subject to, with the consequence that the later crops increased their productivity due to the research, whilst the MRTs remained stagnated.

Associated to above point, Magrini et al. (2016) points out to the “co-evolution” of cropping systems that have led to the selection/self-reinforcement of some crops over others as well as to “increasing return to adoption” of the dominant crops (e.g., wheat). This may be interpreted as adopting the dominant crops benefit producers with aspects such as innovative research, bespoke machinery, knowledge transfer systems which coupled increasing demand that considers those crops as staples make them attractive to farmers and producers downstream the supply chain.

Figure 4: Implications of lock in of MRTs for their development

Less productivity implied lower profitability, which also brought less use of those crops reducing the possibilities to take advantage of scale economies (i.e., reducing the cost of production per area unit by expanding the level of production) and also increasing the transaction costs (e.g., lower volumes of production are subject to higher marketing costs).

Lower profitability means that MRTs compete with disadvantage with other crops, and therefore, they are not chosen in production plans and do not reach the market in comparison with mainstream crops. The number of products developed from MRTs is limited (in comparison with products made of mainstream crops). The effect on the market is that these crops receive less attention from consumers, and they command prices that are lower to their cost of production, which reinforces their lock in situation.

Whilst it is clear from Figure 4 that there is the need of substantial innovation applied to MRTs, the point is how to proceed to break the vicious circle presented in the Figure. Two approaches to this problem indicate that focusing the efforts on one of the stages of the supply chain is not enough but there is the need to involve several stages. For instance, Meynard et al. (2017) point out that instead of working to increase the sustainability of agriculture and food separately, one should consider addressing them simultaneously. Thus, to enhance biodiversity by increasing the planted area of the MRTs, they should be genetically adapted to the local area and make them familiar to farmers. In addition, the crops should also be promoted to consumers and other agrifood system stakeholders, such as collector centres, food processors, retailers and restaurants.

The second approach, very similar to the previous one but formulated in terms of the design of a value chain, put the emphasis on the strategies of a firm with an innovation (Zilberman et al., 2019). To implement the innovation the entrepreneur needs to think on the procurement of feedstock (intermediate inputs), production and processing, and marketing. It must decide how much to produce, what segments of the supply chain to undertake in-house versus sourcing externally, and what institutions such as contracts and standards it will use to coordinate the suppliers assuring its external sourcing.

As pointed out by the CROPDIVA project strengthening agrobiodiversity on the consumer's plate is just as important as strengthening it in the field. This implies that one should address different aspects of the value chain operation at the same time (e.g., consumer demand, logistics, availability of financial resources). Both upstream activities, such as plant breeding, seed production and agricultural production and downstream activities, such as storage, processing and sales need to be considered¹.

¹ These aspects will be considered in ROTATES in different workpackages.

Situation by project case

This section starts with a brief overview of the employed methodology. It is followed by the ten case studies: six about food and four on feed.

Methodology

This section presents the methodology used in the report. It is important to understand from the outset that the information used for the diagnosis is varied and depended on the data available for each one of the countries of the project. It has been complemented with observations provided by the project's partners.

Focusing on the four crops studied on the project (i.e., cassava, sweet potato, taro and yam) information was searched in online databases considering the cases of food and feed and for their respective countries. In all cases, the focus when compiling the evidence was to consider the entire value chains.

In terms of the aims of the report, it was to collect evidence about the crops' supply (i.e., domestic production and imports) and in particular their challenges and opportunities for expansion. In several cases (e.g., cassava made pasta or feed) where information for a particular country was limited it was expanded by considering evidence produced outside Europe. This helped identifying any limitation that may affect the supply.

In addition, information was searched considering the keywords "consumer response" and "consumer acceptance" to find articles focusing on the consumer response or interest regarding the MRT crops. Another search related to consumers was about their preference for organic products. This was due to the fact the focus of the study in several of the project's countries was organic sweet potatoes and not just sweet potatoes, which were a well-known product in the countries. This helped to identify economic and social factors that may help or hamper the consumer acceptance of MRTs based foods.

The qualitative information compiled from the literature review was complemented by quantitative information from FAOSTAT, Eurostat, CyStat (Cyprus Statistical Office) and COMTRADE (United Nations Commodity Trade database). The main purpose of this was to establish whether any trend was present, e.g., on areas dedicated to organic crops.

To provide information about consumers' interest for food products with specific attributes such as organics, data about the evolution of the number of launched products with those attributes was accessed from Mintel's Global New Product Database (GNPD). The logic behind this was that food firms invest on new products with particular attributes when they identify that consumers would be interested in products with a particular attribute e.g., gluten free pasta (see Fuller, 2004; Lucas et al., 2021).

To compare the different cases and extract conclusions, a SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) analysis was used as it is a tool frequently utilised to help plan and formulate strategies (Pereira et al., 2021). The SWOT analysis was carried out based on the evidence compiled for each one of the cases. Although the results help to create value along the supply chain by seeing opportunities, neutralise threats, or mitigate their weaknesses, it is important to remember that this is an initial analysis based on existing evidence.

Food cases

This section covers six cases related to food: conventional taro in Cyprus, organic sweet potatoes in France, Greece and Portugal and two processed products: bread made of yam in Guadeloupe and pasta made of a MRT in Italy. For each case, first, the supply issues are covered (i.e., production, imports and where possible

other aspects of the supply chain) and then consumers' issues such as preferences for the food product itself, their interest for organic products, gluten free pasta.

Cyprus - Conventional taro

Taro (*Colocasia esculenta*) is a root vegetable from the family Araceae that are used as vegetables for their corms, leaves, stems and petioles. Taro corms are a food staple in African, Oceanic, East Asian, Southeast Asian and South Asian cultures such as in the case of yams.

As pointed out by Guzzon et al. (2025) taro was introduced to the eastern Mediterranean region by the fourth century BC or even earlier and there are records that during the Crusader and Lusignan Kingdom the cultivation of taro in Cyprus and its consumption was linked with royal feasts. The same reference reports that in the nineteenth century taro in Cyprus was grown as a substitute for potatoes and its cultivation was expanded to mountainous areas. Those fields suitable for taro cultivation showing favourable soil conditions and sufficient availability of water were identified by farmers with vernacular names linked to taro such as kolokaseri (kolokasi is taro in Greek).

Taro fields were frequently hedged with maize. In addition, intercropping systems with vegetable crops were also applied to compensate for the high production cost of taro. Until the beginning of the twentieth century, although taro was widely grown it was done in very small areas. During the first half of the twentieth century, the cultivation area in Cyprus fluctuated between 78 to 170 hectares with important cultivation areas being Morphou, Lapithos-Karavas, Ayios Andronikos (Karpasia) with the latter being the most important and in 1973 the total cultivation area was 220 hectares with an annual production of 6,300 tonnes.

Supply

In Cyprus the supply of taro is made almost exclusively by the domestic production with imports being negligible. Taro is planted in deep, fertile soils with relatively good drainage. The plant thrives in kokkinochoria areas (i.e., "red soil villages") with a high concentration of red iron oxide in the soil. Crop rotation with cereals and other vegetables species is practiced. Up to 95 per cent of the cultivation area is in Famagusta District, particularly in the village of Sotira, while the remaining 5 per cent is in the coastal areas of Paphos District. In 2021, the value of the production was 906,081€, and the producer's price was 417€/tonne whereas the respective retail price was 830€/tonne i.e., almost twice (Guzzon et al., 2025).

Taro is exclusively vegetatively propagated in Cyprus. Planting material is sown from February to May, on rows with spacing of 90–95 cm with a distance between plants of around 30 cm. Planting material includes side corms, sliced corms and cuttings of the top of the corms including the base of the stem. Farmers argue that the former and the latter material induce earliness. Some farmers also apply bio-stimulants to promote early maturation.

Plants are grown on raised beds which are created when taro plants reach 70 to 80 centimetres height, covering the stems up to 40 centimetres. Due to the high water demands of taro, irrigation is applied with dripping systems. Many farmers applied manure, preferably from chicken, to improve soil texture and fertility. Chemical fertilisers (NPK) are also applied during growing season, and the dosage varies depending on farmers' practices and whether organic manure was incorporated into the field before planting, or not.

Cultivation can be affected by serious pests and diseases infestations. Some farmers apply fungicides at the first stages of the cultivation to control root rots and later pesticides for mole crickets and spider mites are also applied. Weeds are managed chemically and by hoeing. Harvesting begins in early autumn and continues until the following spring.

It is important to highlight that high water demand of taro and the need for summer irrigation, in combination with climate change, frequent drought seasons, and high competition for water from other crops and economic sectors, all constitute an obstacle for expanding taro cultivation.

Figure 5, which combines statistics from FAO (although the source is official statistics) and the Cyprus Statistical Office (CyStat, 2025) shows a historical overview of area, production and yield under taro in the country from 1961 until 2023. The Figure indicates that the evolution of the production has followed that of the area (both showing a steady decrease since the late 1970s) and yields have grown very slowly during the entire period as shown in the regression, which indicates an average growth of 0.168 tonnes/hectare per year.

Regarding the storage of taro, since the plant can remain in the soil without deterioration of the production and the quality, farmers prefer to gradually harvest the yield, according to market demand.

After harvesting, a traditional practice was the peeling of corms by hand using a sharp knife until the surface becomes white (a procedure called ksisimo); however, this practice has become less common because it increases the labour cost and decreases the shelf life of the corms. Current postharvest treatments are restricted to the removal of mud, debris and roots from the surface of the corms.

Figure 5: Cyprus - Area, production and yields of taro 1961-2023

Source: CyStat and FAOSTAT.

Due to the importance of taro cultivation in Famagusta District, particularly in the village of Sotira over the last 50 years, and demand from the local market, Cyprus applied and managed to register taro production from this area as a product of Protected Designations of Origin (PDO), under the name Kolokasi Sotiras/Kolokasi-Poulles Sotiras (EU Regulation 2016/1322). This legislation provides some commercial benefits for the farmers in the area of Sotira. It is expected that farmers in the area will continue growing taro in the future, though expansion of the crop is not expected.

Consumption

Most of the production is consumed locally. Farmers commercialise separately the larger corms which are locally known as mappes and the side corms, known as poulles, with the latter usually commanding higher prices. Cyprus is a modest net exporter of taro, and some minor quantities are sold abroad to satisfy the

demand created by expatriate Cypriots (between 1 to 2 per cent considering the period 2017-2023). Figure 6 shows the per capita consumption of taro, which remains stable.

Taro is very much appreciated by consumers in Cyprus and widely used in the local cuisine. There are many ways in Cyprus to prepare traditional dishes based on taro. The most common one is a casserole stew with tomato sauce, called kolokasi yiakhni. There are some variants of this dish depending on the ingredients, the most common ones being celery, carrots, tomatoes and meat (pork, chicken or lamb). Another traditional dish is taro cooked in the casserole with tomato sauce, placing, on the top of it, grapevine leaves stuffed with rice, mince and herbs. This dish is called 'kolokasi me koupepia'. Fried poulles, cooked with wine and served with coriander seeds, is also a popular taro-based dish.

Figure 6: Cyprus - Annual per capita consumption of taro

Source: Based on FAOSTAT, CyStat data.

Taro has many health benefits. It is rich in fibre, vitamins B6 and C, copper, niacin, and zinc. It is widely used in many dishes, including bubble tea, but it is best enjoyed when cooked. If eaten raw, it can cause a burning sensation in the throat, kidney stones, and gout. Taro contains oxalate, which can lead to kidney stones and gout. It may cause a stinging sensation if eaten raw, so it is best to cook it thoroughly before consuming it. (Home health up, 2023).

Highlights

- The supply of taro is made almost exclusively by domestic production; a minor part of it is exported and imports are negligible. Data indicate that production have been steadily decreasing.
- Taro has a high demand of water and requires fertiliser to improve soil texture and fertility and during the growing season.
- Cultivation can be affected by serious pests and diseases infestations, so some farmers apply fungicides at the first stages of the cultivation to control root rots and later pesticides. Weeds are managed chemically and by hoeing.
- Socially and culturally, taro is very much appreciated by consumers in Cyprus and widely used in the local cuisine. However, its per capita consumption remains constant.
- Taro has many health benefits (e.g., rich in fibre, vitamins B6 and C, copper, niacin, and zinc) but if eaten raw, it can cause a burning sensation in the throat, kidney stones, and gout.

France - Organic sweet potato²

Sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas*) is recognised as one as a promising option for the French agricultural sector in the face of the escalating effects of climate change on agricultural systems. Its cultivation in France dates only from 1750. It was then cultivated by Richard and Gondouin, gardeners of Louis XV who appreciated the tuber. It came back into fashion around 1796 thanks to Joséphine de Beauharnais, who had it grown in Malmaison for her table (Birlouez, 2023). The crop continues to gain in popularity among French producers for its agronomic qualities, as well as among consumers, thanks to its gustatory and nutritional qualities.

Supply

The supply of sweet potatoes in France still relies heavily on imports. However, local production is increasing to meet the growing demand for consumption. Specific annual tonnage varies; the industry has seen significant expansion over the last five years. In this sense, sweet potatoes are already included in the national agricultural census conducted every 20 years. During the local production season, which lasts from September to January, French sweet potatoes account for only about 40 per cent of the total market supply.

Information about the evolution of production of sweet potatoes in France is scarce. Kanso (2025) indicates that their cultivation is relatively new and production levels are still low and hard to predict. Her thesis indicates that the sector had a significant start in 2011 and is characterised by fragmentation and a lack of structure, with its origins lying in individual trial-and-error initiatives. Moreover, its value chain is an evolving and multifaceted system that has experienced considerable expansion and notable development in recent years. Sweet potato farming is marked by diversity with regard to farm typology (small and large farms), production mode (conventional and organic), and distribution channels (short and long).

Kanso (2025) also indicates that some reports state that French production reached around 20,000 tonnes in certain years, with many, though not all, farms transitioning to more industrial-scale (organic and conventional), and organic cultivation. The production seems to have steadily increased to 24,000 tonnes in 2024 when compared to an estimated volume of 10,000 tonnes in 2018.

As regards growing practices, sweet potato is grown using vine cuttings (slips) in sandy soils, with harvests taking place from late August through to early spring. It is considered a difficult, labour-intensive crop, often requiring manual or mechanical weed control. Production faces challenges such as weather variability (heavy rains) and the need to manage pests.

The estimated cultivation area is 500 hectares with approximately 30,000 plants/hectare on average and a yield of about 1 kg tuber/plant (i.e., a yield of 30 tonnes/hectare). The cultivation is concentrated in the south of the country, especially in (Occitanie, Nouvelle-Aquitaine and Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur (PACA)) with marginal cultivation in the western regions like (Pays de la Loire, Bretagne and Normandie). The expansion is driven by the adoption of orange skinned varieties like (Beauregard, Orléans and Jewell). Of particular importance is the Beauregard variety, with its excellent resistance to diseases, high yields and adaptability to different soils and climates

The increasing demand for sweet potatoes in France led to the development of a supply network for seedling primarily structured around Voltz Maraîchage, which now provides sweet potatoes in different varieties and certified. Moreover, several cooperatives like the Coopérative d'utilisation des matériels agricoles (CUMA) also play a very important role in supporting farmers and agricultural activities and practices.

There is no information about the production of organic sweet potatoes in France; however, data for the share of area under organic farming in the country shows a positive trend, reaching 10 per cent in 2022 (Figure 7).

² This section heavily relies on Fatima Kanso's Master thesis (2025), who carried out an evaluation of the French sweet potato sector.

Figure 7: France - Share of area under organic farming

Source: Eurostat.

As mentioned, the supply of sweet potatoes in France depends on imports. Within the European Union, France is the third largest importer (being The Netherlands and Germany, the top two) with an approximately average 61.4 thousand tonnes imported for the period 2020 to 2024, although in 2024 France imported slightly less (59.4 thousand tonnes). Figure 8 shows their evolution, which clearly indicates a significant increase over time.

Imports of sweet potatoes come from countries outside the French harvest season such as the United States, China, Spain, Egypt, the Netherlands, Portugal and Israel (three of them within the EU). This brings a high degree of competitiveness to the market. These countries offer a diverse supply, which is characterised by low prices combined with excellent quality (Kanso, 2025). The lower prices reflect the effects of a more suitable climate, more accessible labour and lower production costs. A notable development in this context is the increase of Egypt in the French market, which in the marketing year July 2024-June 2025 represent 51.5 per cent of the country imports (East Fruit, 2025).

Figure 8: France - Imports of sweet potatoes

Source: FAOSTAT.

Concerning the distribution, the initiatives are mainly led by small producers who sell their products through short distribution channels. However, some cooperatives and large groups are also venturing into the production of this tuber and are seeking to develop longer distribution chains. According to Kanso (2025) there is a significant difference between the prices in the short and long distribution channels; for example, the price of sweet potato in short distribution channel is around 3 €/Kg, whereas in long distribution channels it varies between 1.30 and 1.50 €/Kg.

As regards the processing stage of the supply chain, Kanso (2025) indicates that there is a growing interest in developing the processing sector in France because the higher demand for sweet potatoes rises. Processing includes a variety of products such as sweet potato chips, puree, baked and fries with each product attracting the specific market segments. In addition, sweet potatoes can also be processed into flour, biscuits, bread, juice and in a gratin, or even in muffins.

According to Kanso (2025), the sector is subject to numerous constraints, including the absence of coordination among the relevant parties, inadequate technical assistance, insufficient infrastructure for storage and processing, sensitivity to local pests, harsh winters that require short-cycle varieties, tuber curing and pre-rooted seed plants. It also suffers competition from foreign entities.

Consumption

There is a growing interest from French consumers on sweet potatoes (Escriba, 2023). In recent years, the crop has gained in popularity due to its nutritional qualities as sweet potatoes are rich in beta-carotene, vitamin A, fibre and antioxidants.

In addition, sweet potatoes also provide an opportunity for consumers to diversify their diets something that is reflected in the increasing number of recipes. The past ten years have seen an important increase in the consumption of sweet potatoes in France due to a combination of interest in healthy foods, dietary changes, the growing interest in plant-based diets, and the impact of globalization in the culinary arts, as well as the discovery of recipes using sweet potatoes during travel and cultural exchanges.

The consumption has also been boosted by the growing interest in exotic foods and taste diversity. Indeed, while the Research and Innovation Institute (cited in Kanso, 2025) notes that its consumption increased by 18 per cent between the pre-Covid period (2018–2019 season) and the post-health crisis period (2021–2022), this change is part of a long-term trend.

The most popular varieties amongst consumers are those with pink skin and orange flesh (i.e., Beauregard variety) and also the demand for organic sweet potato increases, as they are considered visually appealing and versatile in culinary applications. There are many reasons for this appeal. First, their vibrant colour is an aesthetic appeal for many. In addition, their sweet flavour and tender texture when cooked are taste criteria that meet the preferences of many consumers.

As the ROTATES project focuses on organic sweet potato, it is important to explore consumers' interest on organic products. Figure 9 provides an indication by considering the share of launched products with the organic attribute in a category within the total number of launched products in the category. As shown in the Figure from 2022 the share of products with the organic attributes have shown a slow decrease (an exception is the noodles category, which is a very small one).

Figure 9: France - Share of launched organic products by category

Source: Mintel's Global New Product Development Database.

Highlights

- Information about the production of sweet potatoes in France is scarce with some reports indicate it that it has grown from to 10,000 tonnes in 2018 to 24,000 tonnes in 2024 with many, though not all, farms transitioning to more industrial-scale, organic, and conventional, and organic cultivation.
- It is considered a difficult, labour-intensive crop, often requiring manual or mechanical weed control. Production faces challenges such as weather variability (heavy rains) and the need to manage pests.
- The supply of sweet potatoes in France depends on imports (59.4 thousand tonnes in 2024).
- Culturally, there is a growing interest from French consumers on sweet potatoes due to its nutritional qualities as they are rich in beta-carotene, vitamin A, fibre and antioxidants.
- Sweet potatoes also provide an opportunity for consumers to diversify their diets something that is reflected in the increasing number of recipes.
- The share of launched products with the organic attribute have shown a slow decrease approximately since the COVID pandemic, which may indicate consumers are only modestly interested in those products or might be an economic issue (e.g., prices or income).

Greece - Organic sweet potato

The first documented evidence of sweet potatoes in Greece comes from the late 16th century. As Greece was part of the Ottoman Empire during this time, sweet potatoes likely arrived via trade networks through Turkey or the Middle East (Ivanovich, 2024).

Supply

Greece has a Mediterranean climate characterised by hot, dry summers and mild, rainy winters, which makes growing tropical root vegetables like sweet potatoes a challenge. Nevertheless, some areas of Greece can support sweet potato cultivation on a small scale during the hot summer months. Sweet potato cultivation is particularly concentrated in the regions of Ilia, Achaia, and Messenia, which account for roughly 68 per cent of national production.

Figure 10 shows that although yields have shown an increasing trend since the late 1990s (maybe indicating improvements in cultivation technology), the area planted has remained stable (i.e., without any trend), although with high variability. The result is also stagnated and variable overall production. The latest information from the FAO estimates that Greece harvested about 8.3 thousand tonnes of sweet potatoes in 2020.

On the Greek mainland, sweet potatoes are usually planted in May and harvested in late September or October before the winter cold arrives. Irrigation is needed to provide sufficient moisture. The most common Greek sweet potato variety is the orange-fleshed Beauregard.

Farmers in Greece are capitalising on the rising demand in both local, and in particular, in international markets. Nevertheless, sweet potato production in Greece is still very low (Ivanovich, 2024). Farmers find that sweet potatoes can yield substantial profits despite their higher production costs. The expected selling price ranges between €0.50 and €0.60 per kilogram, making sweet potatoes a potentially lucrative crop for local farmers, as a response, cultivation has grown from just a few hectares to over 120 hectares.

Figure 10: Greece - Area, production and yields of sweet potatoes

Source: FAOSTAT.

The crop is favoured for being relatively low maintenance, though it requires significant water during the summer. Key challenges include high production costs, potential for crop losses due to pests (worms) in wet years, and ensuring consistent, high-quality yields. The industry is seeing a shift toward more professionalized farming to boost export volumes, with a growing focus on organic production to meet European demand. Figure 11, which presents the share of area under organic production shows a significant increasing since 2016, and in particular, since 2020.

Figure 11: Greece - Share of area under organic farming

Source: Eurostat.

While production is increasing, growers face competition from cheaper Egyptian imports, the most important competitor for this crop. Exports are increasing to countries like Germany, Spain, and Cyprus. Figure 12 presents the country’s imports and exports of sweet potatoes, which show that since 2008 imports have consistently been above than exports.

Figure 12: Greece – Foreign trade of sweet potatoes

Source: FAOSTAT.

Consumption

Greeks enjoy sweet potatoes baked, mashed, fried into fritters or chips, included in casseroles, pureed into soups, and used in desserts. However, sweet potatoes have not become truly mainstream in Greek cooking and are treated as more of a novelty ingredient.

The demand for sweet potatoes has surged, both domestically and internationally. Greece’s sweet potatoes are increasingly exported to countries such as Germany, Spain, and Cyprus, where they are well-received due

to their quality and taste. In fact, recent market analysis shows that exports of Greek sweet potatoes have grown by over 25 per cent year-on-year, driven by rising consumer interest in healthy and locally sourced products.

Figure 13 presents the importance of organic products in selected food categories using information about the annual number of launched. In general, there is not any trend on the evolution of the share of organic products and that remains under 15 per cent. This seems in agreement with the results of Diagourtas et al. (2022), who compare the incentives behind purchasing organic in Greece and Sweden. The authors find that consumers in Sweden more frequently purchase organic foods than consumers in Greece. Environmental protection and ethical values increase the odds for Swedish organic food consumers to buy organic food products whilst health consciousness and family well-being are perceived as factors that increase the odds for Greek organic food consumers to buy organic foods. It is important to note that sociodemographic factors do not play a pivotal role for consumer behaviour in relation to organic food in both countries.

Figure 13: Greece - Share of launched organic products by category

Source: Mintel's Global New Product Development Database.

Highlights

- Greece's mediterranean climate makes growing tropical root vegetables like sweet potatoes a challenge. Nevertheless, some areas of Greece can support sweet potato cultivation on a small scale during the hot summer months.
- Yields show an increasing trend since the late 1990s whilst the area planted has remained stable (i.e., without any trend), although with high variability. The result is a stagnated and variable production. The latest information from the FAO estimates Greece production in 8.3 thousand tonnes (in 2020).
- The crop is favoured for being relatively low maintenance, though it requires significant water during the summer. Key challenges include high production costs, potential for crop losses due to pests (worms) in wet years, and ensuring consistent, high-quality yields.
- The industry is seeing a shift toward more professionalised farming to boost export volumes, with a growing focus on organic production to meet European demand.
- While production is increasing, growers face competition from cheaper Egyptian imports. Exports are increasing to countries like Germany, Spain, and Cyprus. Since 2008 imports have consistently been above than exports.
- Culturally, Greeks enjoy sweet potatoes baked, mashed, fried into fritters or chips, included in casseroles, pureed into soups, and used in desserts. However, sweet potatoes have not become truly mainstream in Greek cooking and are treated as more of a novelty ingredient.

- In general, there is no trend on the evolution of the share of launched products with the organic attribute, which remains under 15 per cent (this may be due to economic factors such as prices and income).

Guadeloupe - Conventional yam bread³

The focus of this section is yam (*Dioscorea*) bread in Guadeloupe, which is an insular overseas territory located in the French West Indies. Yam is a staple food in many tropical countries, particularly in Africa, the Caribbean and the South Pacific. They have brown tough skins, and the flesh can vary in colour – anything from white to yellow to purple – depending on the variety. Note that the term 'yam' is often used in the United States to describe the sweeter, orange sweet potato.

Supply

Although a traditional crop in Guadeloupe, yam in 2024 represented only 0.6 per cent of the total agricultural surface of the island. Most of the area was dedicated to sugarcane (25.9 per cent), grass (24.6 per cent) and bananas (4.3 per cent). As shown in Figure 14, in the last forty years, the production and cultivated area have decreased significantly, revealing the decline of the sector (AGRESTE, 2024).

Figure 14: Guadeloupe - Area, production and yields of yams

Source: AGRESTE.

According to Barlagne (2014), during that period, the production and consumption of yams was highly impacted by the discovery of long-lasting soil pollution by chloride chlordecone, a pesticide used from 1972 to 1993 by banana planters in the southwest of the island. The pollutant does not spread homogeneously in all crops; edible parts of tuber crops are more contaminated if they are grown in contact with polluted soil and the soil pollutant content is high. This led to recommendations of restrictive cultivation.

³ This section relies heavily on Carla Barlagne’s PhD dissertation (2014) and subsequent papers Barlagne et al. (2015) and Barlagne et al. (2016).

It should be noted that that the contaminated soils only represented 10 per cent of agricultural area of the island and yams can still be grown on rest of the island. However, the lack of traceability and presence of an informal market have created issues in the eyes of the consumers.

It is estimated that local yams cover about 78 per cent of the Guadeloupe's demand, the gap between local production and demand being covered by imports. Yams are also the most demanded staples on the external market since their imports represent 85 per cent of the total volume of the imported staples (Barlagne, 2016).

Regarding the varieties of yam, it is important to highlight that there is not a standardised type of yam. This reflects the diversity of the species and varieties present in Guadeloupe. Most of yams are sold through small marketing chains and there is little information is available to consumers about yam varieties, the mode of production, or the origin and cooking characteristics of these varieties.

At the same time, the traceability of yam in local supermarkets is not always warranted and misleading uses of variety names and origins have been reported. Nevertheless, an inter-professional agricultural association has been created in 2009 to better organise fruits and vegetables sectors (including yams). One of the aims of this association is to encourage local production and increase the visibility of local products on the markets. In this context, implementing quality in the yam value chain thanks to labels appeared to be a valuable mean to increase consumers' awareness regarding the product and a relevant way to federate yam farmers.

According to Barlagne (2016), the yam sector in Guadeloupe suffers from the following problems: (i) heavy constraints on production, primarily due to parasitism and high production costs and (ii) poor organisation of the sector.

There is little information about the supply of yam bread. However, it is important to note that it does not require yam flour but fresh yams (Cursa, 2025), therefore, whatever factor that affects yam also affects yam bread. Another interesting aspect is that yam bread recipe requires 500 grams of yam together with 1 kilogram of wheat flour (other ingredients are fresh yeast, sugar, salt, water, and olive oil), which does not imply a substitution of wheat by yam.

The best yam variety for bread are purple yams, which are known for their sweet flavour and nutty aroma, they are a popular choice for creating a unique and flavourful bread (Love and Harvest, 2026). Another possible variety for bread is the yellow yam, which offers a different flavour profile that may appeal to some bakers. These varieties can enhance the taste and texture of yam bread.

Consumption

According to Barlagne (2014) the demand for yam has declined steadily since the consumption of local yam decreased from 23 to 15 kilograms per person per year between 1985 and 2006 (consumption per capita calculated from official statistical sources on population and yam production). In Guadeloupe, traditional starchy staples often referred to as "bread" or "ground provisions" include cassava-based Kassav (flatbread), fried Bokit (a sandwich made of fried wheat dough), and boiled root vegetables like yam (igname). Yam, along with sweet potato and breadfruit, is a staple ground provision served alongside meat or fish dishes, providing a nutritious, locally sourced, and starchy accompaniment to meals.

A study in 2010 (Observatoire Régional de la Santé de Guadeloupe, 2010) about food habits in Guadeloupe revealed that yam, despite its character of staple, is consumed by only a small proportion of the population, which has adopted a diet based on a European model and food that can be prepared more easily compared to other imported fruits and vegetables such as apples or potatoes, yam suffers from a lack of marketing that could enhance its value. Today, the typical consumer does not know about the great diversity of species and varieties that can be found on farms, and for him, yam is a basic product. This lack of information leads the consumer to believe that the overall quality of the product is not reliable even though the differences that can be observed at the cooking and eating stages are simply due to differences between species and varieties.

It is important to note that the same factors that affect the consumption of yam also affect the consumption of yam bread, as the bread requires fresh yams. In this sense, yam consumption has been affected by, first, changes in people's diets and, second, a lack of consumer confidence in the sanitary quality of local yams. The latter is due to the already mentioned contamination of some areas of the island by a persistent pesticide used in the southwestern part of the island (south Basse-Terre) control the banana weevil. Lack of information on product traceability as well as the importance of informal market, make consumers suspicious about yam's sanitary quality.

Another aspect to consider when trying to increase the demand for yam bread is consumers preference for wheat bread. Bread consumption in Guadeloupe as in the rest of French West Indies (Martinique and French Guiana) is heavily influenced by French culture, where the baguette and various bread products are deeply ingrained in daily life and diet. Mirroring mainland France, baguettes are a daily staple, often purchased fresh from local bakeries.

As indicated by Barlagne et al. (2016), the literature on yam consumption is scarce. Existing studies highlighted the role of consumers' socio-demographic characteristics as determinants of yam consumption and the role of product quality (e.g., freshness, size, shape, colour of the flesh) in price formation. Her study indicated the complexity of yam quality in the eyes of consumers. Quality first appealed to the senses of the study participants, and it referred to a wide range of attributes of yams. They also described the attributes with a range of values that reflected the heterogeneity of their preferences.

Participants defined the quality of yams with several sensory and visual attributes: taste preferences (sweet, bitter, neutral), particular individual perceptions of the taste (refined, wild), an external aspect of the tuber free of damages and a small or medium size of tubers (depending on family size). Yam texture also plays an important role, for example, the firm varieties were suitable for fries or gratin, while the tender varieties were more suitable for puree. Both types of texture were suitable for boiling, but the cooking time had to be adjusted to the type of texture (longer for the firm varieties). This clearly shows the importance of the cooking mode for defining yam quality. However, while participants mentioned the yam varieties to illustrate the specific desired traits or cooking modes, some of them were wrong in identifying the varieties used as supporting examples for the discussion.

It is important to highlight that few people in Guadeloupe are aware of the diversity of yams. Therefore, improving the level of information available to the consumers might help them make choices that better suit their needs and so motivate them to purchase and eat more yams. For example, as it is made for potatoes, packaging yams and giving information regarding the suitability of the different varieties for different cooking modes (i.e., mashed, fried or boiled) would help consumers to make informed choices.

Highlights

- Although a traditional crop in Guadeloupe, yam in 2024 represented only 0.6 per cent of the total agricultural surface of the island. Most of the area was dedicated to sugarcane (25.9 per cent), grass (24.6 per cent) and bananas (4.3 per cent). The production and cultivated area have decreased significantly, revealing the decline of the sector.
- The yam sector in Guadeloupe suffers from the following problems: (i) heavy constraints on production, primarily due to parasitism and high production costs and (ii) poor organisation of the sector.
- The production and consumption of yam in the island was highly impacted by the discovery of long-lasting soil pollution associated to banana production. Lack of traceability and the presence of an informal market have contributed to the stagnation of the product.
- Despite that there are many varieties of yam, consumers are unaware of their differences, and this can provide a possibility a marketing campaign that can expand the demand and create greater value for producers.
- Local yams cover about 78 per cent of the Guadeloupe's demand and the gap between local production and consumption is covered by imports.

- There is little information about the supply of yam bread. However, as yam bread requires fresh yams all the problems associated to yam (lack of trust about their safety) are carried also to the bread yam.

Italy - Conventional pasta from an MRT

As pointed out by Romano et al. (2021) dried pasta is a wheat-based staple food that is also the second most consumed food worldwide, due to its low cost, nutritional composition, versatility, easy preparation and storage, extended shelf life as well as desirable sensory attributes.

Traditionally, durum wheat semolina is the elective raw material for pasta making, due to its intense yellow colour and, remarkably, to the unique and high protein content, inducing high functionality and the appropriate dough structure properties. Semolina is highly used despite its high starch digestibility, its gluten content and its low content in vitamins, fibre and bioactive compounds. However, pasta also has a long-standing research history of partial or total substitution of the durum wheat semolina with flour from other cereals or plants and with raw materials from animal sources (e.g., cricket power).

According to Romano et al. (2021) two main driving forces have been identified within the studies applied to either supplementation or replacement of durum wheat in pasta: (1) To increase the nutritional value of pasta, by partial replacement/enrichment of semolina with highly nutritious raw materials such as dietary fibre and a wide range of unconventional ingredients into dried pasta recipe and (2) to prevent allergenicity/intolerance, in particular to gluten, by the complete replacement of semolina with gluten-free raw materials such as rice, sorghum, cassava and corn flours into dried pasta formulation.

This section starts reviewing the supply of pasta in Italy, first, based on wheat and then the supplementation or replacement of durum wheat. Next information about the consumption of later is presented (e.g., factors regarding its acceptance).

Supply

Italy is the world's leading pasta producer, generating between 3.6 to 4.1 million tonnes annually, which accounts for over two-thirds of all EU production. The industry generates nearly €7 billion in turnover and exporting over 2.2 million tonnes (about 77 per cent) of all EU pasta exports (Eurostat, 2024)⁴. Figure 15 shows the evolution of Italy's total production and exports of pasta based on FAO data.

⁴ It should be noted that the share of Italy's production that is exported differs between FAO and Eurostat. Whilst the former shows that almost all the pasta produced is exported (there are other components of the supply besides production such as change in stocks) as shown in Figure 15, according to Eurostat (2024) it is about 77 per cent.

Figure 15: Italy - Production and exports of pasta

Source: FAOSTAT.

Whilst Italy leads in production, it imports significant amounts of wheat, as domestic durum wheat production only covers a small portion of demand. Key production hubs include Parma and the Gragnano region, which utilise high-quality durum wheat semolina. Major producers like Barilla (based in Parma) operate massive facilities capable of producing 330 thousand tonnes annually.

Moving to alternative pasta, Italy is a premier producer, leveraging traditional techniques to replicate conventional pasta's texture and taste. Alternative pasta includes gluten-free, plant-based, protein-enriched, and other non-conventional pasta types. In Italy, this segment is expanding due to rising health consciousness, plant-based diets, and sustainability concerns.

It should be highlighted that none of the ROTATES' MRTs appears importantly on the market for alternative pasta. Nevertheless, they have been mentioned in some studies such as Marengo et al., 2018, who present a case for enriching gluten-free rice pasta with soybean and sweet potato flours; Galassi et al. (2023), who studied sorghum, cassava, and durum wheat to produce wholegrain spaghetti to add improve its nutritional and sensorial aspects and to combine Italian and foreign tastes; and Baah et al. who evaluate the suitability of cassava and sweet potato flours for pasta production.

According to Market Research (2024), while wheat-based pasta still dominates with about 91.8 per cent share, alternative pasta collectively accounts for roughly 8–9 per cent of the market, reflecting a gradual but steady shift toward healthier and specialty options. Moreover, gluten-free pasta, a major category within alternative pasta, is expected to be growing at a rate of 3.41 per cent from 2025 to 2032.

Romano et al. (2021) point out that added materials are egg, vegetables such as tomato, spinach or carrots, all of them having more a flavouring and colouring than a technological scope. On the other side, in modern industry, the use of high functionality ingredients for value addition to pasta is a developing field of research to perform innovative product categories and to attract new classes of consumers. Some ingredients, that is, legume flour, are well suited either to improve nutritional value or to reduce adverse reactions to pasta. In fact, the use of legume flour to enrich or make gluten free pasta products has been based, respectively, on the high protein content/high lysine abundance (limited in cereals) and on the contemporary absence of gluten. These products are nowadays already on the market and are gaining large popularity. utilise ingredients like corn, rice, quinoa, and legumes in dedicated, safe facilities to create diverse, allergen-free shapes.

Major Italian manufacturers of alternative pasta are Farabella (Bioalimenta), based in Abruzzo, producing over 70 shapes in a dedicated allergen-free factory; Andriani (Felicia), features 8 dedicated production lines for various gluten-free, legume-based pastas; Pasta di Venezia, specializes in fresh, organic, gluten-free pasta; Le Veneziane (Molino di Ferro) is known for non-GMO corn-based pasta; Pangea S.r.l. focuses on varied blends including oat, hemp, and chestnut. However, note that large producers of conventional pasta including Barilla, De Cecco, Pasta Zara, and Buitoni, are actively expanding their alternative pasta portfolios to capture this growing segment. Companies are investing in new formulations, plant-based ingredients, and gluten-free options to meet evolving consumer preferences.

Romano et al. (2021) indicate that the increasing demand for innovative pasta products is encouraging research on novel raw and processed materials to meet the consumer demand in terms of nutritional, sensory and technological value of pasta. It is important to note that major challenges for pasta industry are now to increase food healthiness but keeping high sensory attributes and cooking performances. In this regard, the appropriate selection of ingredients is fundamental, since pasta formulation directly influences its quality and structural features but, in turn, also affect content, digestibility and ultimately the bioavailability of macro-nutrients (starch, proteins) and micro-nutrients (minerals, phyto-chemicals). Moreover, it is important to perform an accurate cost/benefit economic analysis of the upcycling related to the new pasta formulations. From this basis, research efforts are now to be focused to exploit novel pasta formulations able to optimize technological and sensory attributes at different replacement levels (i.e., sufficient to enhance nutritional profile) of semolina always taking in mind the consumer attitude and consumer choice drivers towards these innovative pasta types.

Galassi et al. (2023) point out that the Mediterranean diet is changing to keep up with the increasingly multiethnic Italian society. With food being considered as a means of integration, innovative foods capable of mixing different raw materials could be of interest. In this work, some of the most consumed African foods such as sorghum, cassava, and durum wheat were used to produce wholegrain spaghetti to improve their nutritional and sensorial aspects and to combine Italian and foreign tastes. Their study considered several pasta formulations (cassava, semolina, cassava: semolina, cassava: sorghum, cassava: durum wheat whole meal, sorghum: semolina) which were developed and compared based on their content of proteins, total starch, resistant starch, amylose, fibre, total antioxidant capacity, ash, cooking quality and sensorial characteristics. They noted that the enrichment of cassava flour with durum wheat and sorghum wholegrain enhanced the total antioxidant capacity, protein, and fibre content with respect to a pasta made entirely of cassava. They also added that although the obtained pasta samples were interesting for their nutritional aspects, further adjustments are needed in the pasta-making process to improve pasta quality.

Consumption

Italians are the world's highest consumers of pasta, with approximately 23 kilograms per capita annually. As indicated by Xhakollari et al. (2025), there is an increasing popularity of the gluten-free diet has spurred the expansion of the market for gluten-free products. However, research on consumers' preferences for those products, especially pasta, is still very limited.

Xhakollari et al. (2025) paper identified preferences for gluten free pasta among celiac consumers based on the sensorial description of four gluten free pasta samples. A sensorial study with a professional panel provided a description of the pasta samples and selected the legume pasta as the most preferred one. Subsequently, the definitions of the pasta samples were used to understand celiac consumer choices and willingness to pay for legume pasta. Results showed that most participants chose the mix of legume and cereal pasta. Additionally, willingness to pay for legume pasta was negatively influenced if celiac consumers assigned high importance to taste, and participants choosing the legume and cereal mix pasta had a higher willingness to pay for the legume option.

Nazzaro et al. (2025) studied consumers' preferences regarding the use of ancient grains (e.g., spelt, khorasan wheat, einkorn, emmer, millet, barley, teff, oats, and sorghum) for pasta production. Those grains are increasingly recognized for their nutritional value, environmental sustainability, and connection to traditional

agriculture. Their study examines Italian consumers' awareness, purchasing habits, and willingness to pay for ancient grain pasta, focusing on the influence of product origin, price, and flour type on preferences using an online survey conducted with 3020 Italian household grocery shoppers. The results indicated that a significant portion of respondents reported familiarity with ancient grains, perceiving them as "less refined" and "more digestible"; pasta emerged as the most purchased product. Their analysis also indicated that product origin as the most influential factor, followed by price, with flour type having comparatively lower influence. Notably, consumers that were more familiar with ancient grains showed a slight preference for ancient flour types and were less sensitive to price. Overall, the paper indicated that while origin and price are primary drivers for pasta choices, knowledgeable consumers show greater valuation for flour type and accept higher prices.

In a developing country context (i.e., Nigeria, although applicable to Sub-Saharan Africa), Lawal et al. (2021) studied pasta developed using yellow biofortified cassava has been adjudged as a cost-effective solution to vitamin A deficiency in low- and middle-income countries with high cassava intake such as Nigeria. Attitudes, perception, motives for consumption and perceived barriers were ascertained using focus group discussions and randomised face-to-face interviews, while liking, preference and ranking of the novel food were established through consumer sensory perception. Willingness to consume the new food, low food neophobia (32 per cent), a health-driven consumption pattern, as well as an appreciable acceptance for the developed pasta, was established among the consumers. This highlights that similar studies (i.e., use of MRTs) are carried out in other countries.

Figure 16 shows the evolution of launched organic products in Italy on several categories. The figures do not show any trend, and all the categories are below 30 per cent.

Figure 16: Italy - Share of launched organic products by category

Source: Mintel's Global New Product Development Database.

Highlights

- The alternative pasta segment in Italy is expected to continue gradual growth, driven by health-conscious consumers and innovation in plant-based and gluten-free products. While still a minority compared to traditional wheat pasta, its market share is projected to increase steadily over the next decade.
- While wheat-based pasta still dominates with about 91.8 per cent share, alternative pasta collectively accounts for roughly 8–9 per cent of the market, reflecting a gradual but steady shift toward healthier and specialty options

- Studies indicate that there is an increasing demand for innovative pasta products which is encouraging research on novel raw and processed materials to meet the consumer demand in terms of nutritional, sensory and technological value of pasta.
- It is important to note that major challenges for pasta industry are now to increase food healthiness but whilst keeping high sensory attributes and cooking performances.
- Regarding the interest on organic products the figures do not show any particular trend and the share of launched products with the attribute in all the categories are below 30 per cent. This may be something due to economic factors.

Portugal - Organic sweet potato

According to the Portuguese National Direction of Health (Republica Portuguesa, 2026), the sweet potato originated in Central America and arrived in Europe in the 16th century, being as old in Portugal as the potato. It should be noted that unlike in the case of other European countries, sweet potato is not a minor crop in Portugal, but its organic version is.

Supply

Sweet potato production in Portugal is an important part of the agricultural sector. Figure 17 provides the evolution of the area, production and yields. The area shows an important degree of variability, in general, fluctuating between 100 to 300 hectares.

Figure 17: Portugal - Area, production and yields of sweet potatoes

Source: FAOSTAT.

In contrast to the area, the evolution of production shows approximately two periods: first, a decreasing one from mid-1960s to late 1990s and a second period, after that where production remained stable at relatively low levels, with production around 15 to 20 thousand tonnes as of 2012-2023. Yields remained stable until the late 2000s when it increased significantly with respect to its past.

The main growing areas are in the South-eastern Coastal Area, particularly Aljezur (Algarve) and the Alentejo region. Harvesting and production generally extend from September to April/June, although most harvests take place in October and November, so these are the best months to consume this tuber.

The major varieties include Beauregard (orange-fleshed), Rubina, and the locally renowned Lira (yellow pulp/red skin). The Aljezur region is particularly famous for its sweet potato as the climatic conditions proved to be ideal for its cultivation. This has earned an Indicação Geográfica Protegida label (Protected Geographical Indication).

Figure 18 shows that the share of the area under organic farming has been increasing reaching almost 20 per cent in 2021 and 2022 (the most recent years with information. Although, these data do not necessarily reflect the sweet potato area, it provides some indication of farmers’ interest on organic agriculture.

Figure 18: Portugal - Share of area under organic farming

Source: Eurostat.

Despite high demand, Portuguese producers face challenges with storage, packaging, and increasing production costs, often storing products to wait for better prices.

Figure 19 shows the evolution of exports and imports. For most of the studied period sweet potato was product only domestically traded by since mid-2010s both exports and imports started to show a significantly increasing trend.

Figure 19: Portugal – International trade of sweet potatoes

Source: FAOSTAT.

As shown in Figure 19, it is remarkable the increase of exports, which surpassed the level of imports around 2013, making Portugal a net exporter. This also indicates that the country is taking advantage of increases on the international demand.

Consumption

Ramos (2023) indicates that Portugal's food culture is associated with the Mediterranean diet and lifestyle, where seasonality, frugality, freshness and locality are cornerstones. Sweet potato is used for fresh but most production is processed after cutting and freezing (for dehydrate/desiccate for starch and baby food). Sweet potatoes can be consumed in various ways. The most traditional is boiled, with or without seasonings, as a substitute for other starches (e.g., potatoes, rice, or pasta).

Oliveira et al (2023) studied consumption habits of fruits and vegetables (including sweet potatoes) from organic farming within a convenience sample of Portuguese adults, including reasons for consumption, most valued mode of production sources, frequency of use, knowledge about characteristics and benefits, and information sources. They used an online questionnaire that was shared on social networks. The organic vegetables identified as the most consumed were lettuce (93.5 per cent of the sample), potato (92 per cent), and tomato (92 per cent); the most consumed organic fruits were orange (83 per cent), lemon (82 per cent), and strawberry (82 per cent). Sweet potato ranked 9th (80.6 per cent).

According to the study the strongest motivations to consume organic fruit and vegetables included environmental benefits (57 per cent) and health benefits (94 per cent), namely the prevention of high total cholesterol (71 per cent), the prevention of cardiovascular diseases (69 per cent), and obesity prevention (68 per cent). Regarding the level of information about the nutritional and chemical properties of organic fruit and vegetables, 86 per cent of the respondents consider themselves informed people. Note that there still are 33 per cent of the respondents revealing no concern about the farming practices. As so, there is an opportunity to increase literacy about these products, to raise awareness about the benefits of organic products, and to promote higher consumption of organic products, supported in the arguments of perceived positive impact of organic agriculture on ecosystems and human health.

Figure 20, which focuses on the importance of the organic attribute on launched products, indicates that consumers have interest on organic products. On average, considering all the food and drink products, the share is slightly less than 20 per cent.

Figure 20: Portugal - Share of launched organic products by category

Source: Mintel's Global New Product Development Database.

Highlights

- The area on sweet potatoes shows an important degree of variability, in general, fluctuating between 100 to 300 hectares. Since the late 1990s the production has remained stable at relatively low levels, with production around 15 to 20 thousand tonnes as of 2012-2023. Yields remained stable until the late 2000s when the increased significantly with respect to its past.
- Despite high demand, Portuguese producers face challenges with storage, packaging, and increasing production costs, often storing products to wait for better prices.
- For most of the studied period sweet potato was product only domestically traded by since mid-2010s both exports and imports started to show a significantly increasing trend. In particular, exports have shown a significant increase since then.
- Culturally, in Portugal, sweet potato is used for fresh but most production is processed after cutting and freezing (for dehydrate/desiccate for starch and baby food). Sweet potatoes can be consumed in various ways. The most traditional is boiled, with or without seasonings, as a substitute for potatoes, rice, or pasta.
- Information indicates that consumers have interest on organic fruit and vegetable products. However, the number of products with the organic attribute do not show any trend.

Feed cases

This section covers information for four cases related to feed: conventional taro in Azores Islands and conventional cassava in Canary Islands, Congo and French Guiana. For each crop, first, their characteristics when use as feed are reviewed followed by the current situation in the places where they are going to be studied in the project. The latter was compiled from project partners.

Conventional taro

Taro as feed

This section is based on an article by Team Pashudhan praharee (2024) which explores the veterinary significance of taro (*Colocasia esculenta*) focusing on its nutritional benefits, medicinal properties, and role in animal feed and healthcare.

Taro serves as a valuable feed resource for various livestock species. It is rich in essential nutrients like carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins, and minerals, supporting animal growth and health. Its medicinal properties, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory effects, offer potential benefits in disease management and animal welfare.

Carbohydrates in taro provide energy, while dietary fibre aids in digestion and promotes gastrointestinal health in animals. Proteins present in taro contribute to muscle development and overall growth in animals. Moreover, taro contains vitamins such as vitamin C, vitamin B6, and folate, which are essential for immune function, energy metabolism, and reproductive health in animals. Minerals like potassium, magnesium, and calcium are also abundant in taro, supporting bone health, nerve function, and electrolyte balance in animals.

In addition to its nutritional value, taro possesses various medicinal properties that can benefit animal health. Traditionally, taro has been used in folk medicine to treat various ailments in both humans and animals. The leaves, stems, and corms of taro contain bioactive compounds with pharmacological properties. For instance, taro leaves are rich in antioxidants such as flavonoids and phenolic compounds, which help combat oxidative stress and inflammation in animals. These antioxidant properties may contribute to the prevention of diseases such as cancer and cardiovascular disorders in animals.

Furthermore, taro contains compounds with antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties, which can help animals fight infections and reduce inflammation associated with various health conditions. Research suggests that extracts from taro plants exhibit antibacterial activity against common pathogens, making them potentially useful in veterinary medicine for the treatment of bacterial infections in animals. Additionally, the anti-inflammatory properties of taro may alleviate symptoms of arthritis and other inflammatory conditions in animals, improving their overall well-being.

By incorporating taro into animal diets and utilising its medicinal properties, stakeholders can optimise animal performance, reduce disease risks, and contribute to overall animal well-being. In addition, it is a significant resource with diverse applications in veterinary medicine and animal husbandry, underscoring its importance in veterinary science and agriculture.

Taro serves as a valuable feed resource for various livestock species, including cattle, pigs, poultry, and fish. Taro can be incorporated into animal diets in different forms, including fresh, dried, or processed products such as flour or meal.

The veterinary implications of taro extend beyond its nutritional and medicinal properties to its broader impact on animal husbandry, healthcare, and disease management. By incorporating taro into animal diets, farmers can improve the health, productivity, and profitability of their livestock operations. Furthermore, the cultivation of taro can provide economic opportunities for rural communities engaged in animal husbandry and agriculture.

In regions where animal diseases are prevalent, the nutritional and medicinal properties of taro can help mitigate the impact of such diseases on livestock populations. For example, the antioxidant and antimicrobial properties of taro may enhance the immune response of animals, reducing their susceptibility to infectious diseases. Similarly, the anti-inflammatory properties of taro can alleviate symptoms associated with inflammatory conditions, improving the welfare of affected animals.

Moreover, the cultivation of taro can contribute to sustainable livestock production systems by diversifying feed sources and reducing dependence on conventional feed ingredients. Taro cultivation is relatively low-input and environmentally friendly, requiring minimal chemical inputs and water resources compared to other crops. Therefore, promoting the cultivation and utilization of taro in animal feed can support sustainable agriculture practices and enhance the resilience of livestock production systems to environmental challenges.

Current situation of taro as feed in Azores Island

To the best of our partners knowledge in Azores Island, taro is not currently used as animal feed in the Azores, at least not in a systematic or documented way.

The target species for the work are cattle (bovines), particularly within the Azorean livestock production systems. Currently, cattle feeding in the Azores is mainly based on pasture (fresh grass), complemented with conserved forages (silage and hay) and commercial concentrates, depending on the production system and season.

Regarding the probability of uptake by livestock producers (advantages and challenges), at present, the probability of uptake of taro as animal feed is low. There is currently a scarcity of taro tubers for human consumption, which makes their use in animal feeding unlikely and economically unjustifiable. However, there may be potential interest in the medium to long term regarding taro leaves, which represent an agricultural residue. From the ROTATES partners perspective, the leaves could be explored as a feed resource in the future, provided that their nutritional value, safety (e.g., antinutritional factors), preservation methods, and economic feasibility are properly assessed.

Potential advantages include the valorisation of local agricultural residues and a reduced dependence on imported feed. Challenges include limited availability, lack of tradition and technical knowledge, the presence of antinutritional compounds, and competition with human food uses.

<p>Highlights</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taro is rich in essential nutrients like carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins, and minerals, supporting animal growth and health. Its medicinal properties, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory effects, offer potential benefits in disease management and animal welfare. • By incorporating taro into animal diets and utilising its medicinal properties, stakeholders can optimize animal performance, reduce disease risks, and contribute to overall animal well-being. • Taro is not currently used as animal feed in the Azores, at least not in a systematic or documented way. There is currently a scarcity of taro tubers for human consumption, which makes their use in animal feeding unlikely and economically unjustifiable. However, there may be potential interest in the medium to long term regarding taro leaves, which represent an agricultural residue. • The target species for the work are cattle (bovines), particularly within the Azorean livestock production systems. Currently, cattle feeding in the Azores is mainly based on pasture (fresh grass), complemented with conserved forages (silage and hay) and commercial concentrates, depending on the production system and season. • Potential advantages include the valorisation of local agricultural residues and a reduced dependence on imported feed. Challenges include limited availability, lack of tradition and technical knowledge, the presence of antinutritional compounds, and competition with human food uses.
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Conventional cassava

Cassava as feed

Besides its role as an important staple food for millions of people, cassava is widely used as livestock feed and industrial uses. As feed, cassava is used in the form of fresh cassava leaves and roots (in limited quantities, fresh cassava leaves and roots can be fed to livestock and it is used in Sub-Saharan Africa, Asia and South America), cassava pellets (pelleted cassava roots are used after sun-drying and steaming in Asia and South America) and leaves and root silage (silage produced from cassava leaves and roots are used in Asia and South America).

The cassava roots are sun-dried followed by mechanical peeling and chipping; after that they are processed into pellets for export. To enhance the protein content in cassava-based animal feed, soybean meal or fish meal is added to provide balanced diets for livestock. Cassava meal possesses excellent digestibility due to the presence of naturally occurring lactic acid bacteria and yeasts. In addition, microdoses of hydrogen cyanide present in cassava make enzymes like lactoperoxidase (secreted from, mammary, mucosal, and salivary glands) more efficient in their function as natural antibacterial agents.

Best (1987) reviewed the situation of cassava processing for feed. The enormous potential for using cassava as a feed for all types of livestock has long been recognised, and a large amount of research has been devoted to defining the optimum levels of dry cassava in animal diets and to modifying the plant's chemical and physical properties that restrict its use. The interest within Europe has been as a substitute of cereals, when the price of these is high.

Asian countries are the world's largest exporters of dried cassava, largely in the form of pellets. These countries use, have well-established industries that clean, chip, sun dry, and pellet the roots. In other countries of Asia, Africa, and Latin America, where cassava forms an important part of the staple diet, it is grown principally by small farmers for family consumption or for sale in the local market. It is virtually never dried for animal feed, although the small or large roots that are unsuitable for human consumption are often fed fresh to the household pig.

Jumare et al. (2024) reviewed cassava waste as an animal feed treatment. The motivation was that in many countries, scientists have developed techniques and processing methods to minimise animal feed waste and costs. The agricultural waste from each part of the cassava plant is rich in macronutrients, essential amino acids, vitamins, and minerals, making it a potential candidate to be used as animal feed. However, the significant content of anti-nutritional properties in cassava, which are linked with the indigestibility of the animal, led to controversy regarding the strategy to use cassava as highly commercialized animal feed.

Among the anti-nutritional compounds found in cassava waste, cyanide was found to have the most negative effect on the animals upon feed consumption. Therefore, several strategies to maintain the homeostasis of nutrient and non-nutrient compounds improved the production and commercialization of cassava waste-based animal feed. Physical pretreatment, microbial pretreatment, and fermentation significantly reduced the cyanide content in the cassava waste. In terms of fermentation, solid-state fermentation of moist, solid, non-soluble organic material acts as a nutrient and energy source. Factors such as moisture content, particle size, temperature, pH, media composition, choice of microbial inoculum, and inoculum density were important to increase protein content, improve digestibility, amino acids, enzymes, and vitamins.

The impact of using cassava waste as animal feed replacement was significant on the digestibility, growth performance, and changes in blood parameters of the animals. Despite the challenges in nutrient content and biological action, the accessibility and availability of cassava in different geographical areas also pose significant challenges. Therefore, applying technological advancements, particularly in enhancing the nutritional content and biological mechanisms, is important, with the implementation of advanced research and collaboration with industries and other stakeholders.

Cassava and its residues as animal feed have been well-practiced and farmers feed the animals with cassava peels or sundried wastes as a feed resource to minimize the cyanogenic toxins.

Current situation of cassava as feed in Canary Islands

Cassava has not yet been established in the Canary Islands as a commercial crop for human consumption, so it is not possible to use the by-products for animal feed. Logically, it is not grown directly for animal feed either.

Within the project, the purpose is to focus specifically on small ruminants, including goats and poultry (including laying hens and broiler chickens). More generally, the results obtained could also be extrapolated to other ruminants such as cows, and sheep, and even later, once the relevant experiments have been carried out to other monogastric animals such as swine.

In the Canary Islands, animal feed is based on cereals (corn, oats, barley) and legumes (beans, peas, soybeans), all of which are imported, as local production is negligible. These grains are processed and formulated in different proportions in feed industries for subsequent sale and distribution to livestock farms. For ruminants, fodder or forage, such as lucerne, ryegrass, or cereal straw is also imported as fibrous feed. It is estimated that between 80-90 per cent of livestock feed is imported.

Currently, the chances of cassava being introduced as animal feed are very low. First, it would have to be cultivated as food for human consumption and become widespread. Although there are farmers interested in growing it, the demand is still very low, and it is practically impossible to find plant material for cultivation. It should be noted that there is a growing population of people from other countries in the Canary Islands who consume cassava in their daily diet, but this production is fully imported. By-products for livestock could be obtained from these future cassava crops for human consumption.

As main advantages, from the point of view of animal, cassava is very interesting because of its very high yield and good nutritional quality when the roots (energy carbohydrates) are combined with the aerial part (protein). Moreover, it also has a high concentration of bio-functional compounds.

It should be noted that when introduced to conduct feasibility tests, it was found that although cassava needs moderate amounts of water, once established it was resistant and did not suffer from pests or diseases present in the Canary Islands.

Current situation of cassava as feed in Congo

It is important to note from the outset that in Congo, cassava is primarily used for human consumption (it is the staple food). However, its use in livestock farming is growing as an economic alternative to replace maize, which is often expensive or imported.

Cassava peels are the most common form of use in artisanal and peri-urban areas. Peels resulting from the traditional production of fofou (a traditional dish in West African cuisine, particularly popular in Ghana. It is made from boiled starchy foods like cassava, plantains, or yams, which are pounded until they form a smooth, stretchy dough) are immediately collected to serve as basic feed for pigs, goats, and sheep.

Surplus cassava leaves are used for small ruminants (sheep and goats). In some more structured farming operations, leaf ensilage is practiced preserving nutrient-rich fodder during the dry season.

Additionally, retting water and small debris from the production of cassava paste are sometimes recovered, especially in rural areas, to water or feed pigs in a traditional manner.

Current situation of cassava as feed in French Guiana

Cassava is a common crop in French Guiana. Farmers surely already have a few plants at home or around their homes. Feeding livestock is a very significant cost for farmers, in addition to being dependent on deliveries.

The use of cassava in animal feed is not extended in French Guiana and only few farmers use it mainly for chickens, ducks and pigs. Most of the animal feed relies on imports from France. Cassava represents a very interesting alternative for achieving food sovereignty or at least reducing dependence on food imports.

Regarding the cattle farming, the systems are mostly extensive, but there are complementary inputs with fodder where cassava could be used. Most producers would adopt cassava as a feed supplement if they were shown its benefits, how to do it exactly (preparing cassava) and if it does not involve too many additional constraints and costs.

Highlights

- As feed, cassava is used in the form of fresh cassava leaves and roots, cassava pellets and leaves and root silage.
- Among the anti-nutritional compounds found in cassava waste, cyanide was found to have the most negative effect on the animals upon feed consumption. Therefore, several strategies to maintain the homeostasis of nutrient and non-nutrient compounds improved the production and commercialization of cassava waste-based animal feed.
- The impact of using cassava waste as animal feed replacement was significant on the digestibility, growth performance, and changes in blood parameters of the animals. Despite the challenges in nutrient content and biological action, the accessibility and availability of cassava in different geographical areas also pose significant challenges. Therefore, applying technological advancements, particularly in enhancing the nutritional content and biological mechanisms, is important, with the implementation of advanced research and collaboration with industries and other stakeholders.
- Cassava has not yet been established in the Canary Islands as a commercial crop for human consumption, so it is not possible to use the by-products for animal feed. Logically, it is not grown directly for animal feed either. Animal feed is based on cereals (corn, oats, barley) and legumes (beans, peas, soybeans), all of which are imported, as local production is negligible. For ruminants, fodder or forage, such as lucerne, ryegrass, or cereal straw is also imported as fibrous feed.
- In Congo, cassava is primarily used for human consumption (it is the staple food). However, its use in livestock farming is growing as an economic alternative to replace maize, which is often expensive or imported. Cassava peels are the most common form of use in artisanal and peri-urban areas.
- Cassava is a common staple crop in French Guiana. Farmers probably already have a few plants at home or around their homes. Feeding livestock is a very significant cost for farmers, in addition to being dependent on deliveries. The use of cassava in animal feed is not extended in French Guiana and only few farmers use it mainly for chickens, ducks and pigs. Most of the animal feed relies on imports from France. Cassava represents an alternative for achieving food sovereignty or reducing dependence on food imports.
- The interest within Europe has been as a substitute of cereals, when the price of these is high.

Discussion

Table 3 presents a strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) analysis (Pereira et al., 2021). The purpose is to process the information collected in the previous section and classify it the aforementioned categories.

The SWOT analysis is useful because in most of the cases we are considering the introduction of almost new products and therefore it is important to understand factors helping or hampering their position in the target market.

Table 3: SWOT analysis of the different cases

Case	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Cyprus - Conventional taro (food)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is a well-known crop in Cyprus. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High water demand, need for summer irrigation. Cultivation can be affected by serious pests and diseases infestations. Production has steadily decreased. Most of the production is consumed locally and remains stable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cyprus is a modest net exporter of taro. Taro has many nutritional qualities that can attract domestic and foreign demand. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate change, frequent drought seasons. High competition for water from other crops and economic sectors.
France - Organic sweet potato (food)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Although still modest, the French production appears growing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is considered a difficult, labour-intensive crop, often requiring manual or mechanical weed control. Production faces challenges such as weather variability (heavy rains) and the need to manage pests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a growing interest from French consumers on sweet potatoes as shown by the increasing imports. The crop has gained in popularity due to its nutritional qualities as sweet potatoes are rich in beta-carotene, vitamin A, fibre and antioxidants. Sweet potatoes also provide an opportunity for consumers to diversify their diets. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Domestic production needs to compete with imports from the EU and outside the EU, which have lower cost of production. The share of products with the organic attribute have shown a slow decrease, which may indicate consumers are only modestly interested in those products.
Greece - Organic sweet potato (food)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The crop is favoured for being relatively low maintenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The crop requires significant water during the summer. Key challenges include high 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry is seeing a shift toward more professionalized farming to boost export volumes, with 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greece has a Mediterranean climate characterised

		<p>production costs, potential for crop losses due to pests (worms) in wet years, and ensuring consistent, high-quality yields.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sweet potatoes are not mainstream in Greek cooking and are treated as more of a novelty ingredient. 	<p>a growing focus on organic production to meet European demand.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greeks enjoy sweet potatoes baked, mashed, fried into fritters or chips, included in casseroles, pureed into soups, and used in desserts. 	<p>by hot, dry summers and mild, rainy winters, which makes growing tropical root vegetables like sweet potatoes a challenge.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domestic production competes with imports.
<p>Guadeloupe - Conventional yam bread (food)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yam is a well-known crop in Guadeloupe and a diet staple. • The supply has decreased significantly over the years. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The yam sector in Guadeloupe suffers from the following problems: (i) heavy constraints on production, primarily due to parasitism and high production costs and (ii) poor organisation of the sector. • Past contamination cases, lack of traceability and presence of an informal market create issues with consumers. • Note that yam bread uses fresh yam, therefore whatever that affects yam, affects yam bread. • There is little information is available to consumers about yam varieties, the mode of production, or the origin and cooking characteristics of these varieties. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Labelling and traceability open opportunities for the crop at least at the domestic level. • There are many varieties of yam that can be marketed if the consumers are educated in terms of quality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domestic production competes with imports. • Yam also competes with other crops that are more profitable (exportable) such as sugar and bananas. • Yam, despite its character of staple, competes with products typical from a diet based on a European model (e.g., potatoes, wheat bread).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yam is consumed by only a small proportion of the Guadeloupe population. 		
Italy - Conventional pasta from an MRT (food)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The production of pasta has an increasing trend in Italy. • Pasta is a well-known product that is adaptable to many cultures. • There is research in place to produce alternative pasta. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The market of alternative pasta is small in comparison with the conventional one. • The number of cases with MRTs based pasta is still limited and requires further research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The market of alternative pasta is growing as more consumers are discovering the needs of a gluten free diet. • The market is also growing as consumers are more interested on better nutrition. • In the of Europe, increasing immigration creates opportunities for pasta with different flavours. • Analyses indicated that origin and price are primary drivers for pasta choices, knowledgeable consumers show greater valuation for flour type and accept higher prices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pasta made of MRTs crops have to operate in a marketing space is very crowded because it consists of about 9 per cent of the market, which is share with many other ingredients e.g., ancient grains.
Portugal - Organic sweet potato (food)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sweet potatoes are a well-known product in Portugal for producers and consumers. • The organic area has an increasing trend. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Despite high demand, Portuguese producers face challenges with storage, packaging, and increasing production costs, often storing products to wait for better prices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portugal is taking advantage on the increasing in the foreign demand with raising in exports. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although minor a threat, domestic production competes with imports. • Sweet potatoes compete with other crops (conventional and organic)
Azores Island - Conventional taro (feed)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taro is rich in essential nutrients like carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taro is not currently used in Azores Island as animal feed in a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Valorisation of local agricultural residues and a reduced 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently, cattle feeding in the Azores is mainly

	<p>and minerals, supporting animal growth and health.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Its medicinal properties, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory effects, offer potential benefits in disease management and animal welfare. • Taro cultivation is relatively low-input and environmentally friendly, requiring minimal chemical inputs and water resources compared to other crops. Therefore, promoting the cultivation and utilization of taro in animal feed can support sustainable agriculture practices and enhance the resilience of livestock production systems to environmental challenges. 	<p>systematic or documented way.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of tradition and technical knowledge, the presence of antinutritional compounds, and competition with human food uses 	<p>dependence on imported feed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The cultivation of taro can contribute to sustainable livestock production systems by diversifying feed sources and reducing dependence on conventional feed ingredients. 	<p>based on pasture (fresh grass), complemented with conserved forages (silage and hay) and commercial concentrates, depending on the production system and season.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taro Will compete with imported feed.
<p>Canary Islands – Conventional cassava (feed)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is significant amount of information about the use of cassava for feed in different forms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cassava is totally new for Canary Islands as food and feed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A potential opportunity is to use cassava to substitute some of the imported feed. However, this requires a careful comparison in terms of costs and the effects of cassava on animal performance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the Canary Islands, animal feed is based on cereals (corn, oats, barley) and legumes (beans, peas, soybeans), all of which are imported, as local

				<p>production is negligible.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For ruminants, fodder or forage, such as lucerne, ryegrass, or cereal straw is also imported as fibrous feed.
<p>Congo - Conventional cassava (feed)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is significant amount of information about the use of cassava for feed in different forms. • Cassava is already present in the country as food. • Cassava peels are the most common form of use in artisanal and peri-urban areas. Peels resulting from a traditional dish are immediately collected to serve as basic feed for pigs, goats, and sheep. • Surplus cassava leaves are used for small ruminants (sheep and goats). • In some more structured farming operations, leaf ensilage is practiced preserving nutrient-rich fodder during the dry season. • Additionally, retting water and small debris from 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Its use in livestock farming is growing as an economic alternative to replace maize, which is often expensive or imported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of imports are a threat for domestic production.

	the production of cassava paste are sometimes recovered (especially in rural areas) to water or feed pigs in a traditional manner.			
French Guiana - Conventional cassava (feed)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is significant amount of information about the use of cassava for feed in different forms. • Cassava is already present in the country as food. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The use of cassava in animal feed is not extended in French Guiana and only few farmers use it mainly for chickens, ducks and pigs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A potential opportunity is to use cassava to substitute some of the imported feed. • Regarding the cattle farming, the systems are mostly extensive, but there are complementary inputs with fodder where cassava could be used. • Most producers would adopt cassava as a feed supplement if they were shown its benefits, how to do it exactly and if it does not involve too many additional constraints and costs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As in any import substitution case, there is a competition from imports, and the attractiveness of the domestic product depends on prices and the impact of the feed on animal performance.

Although all the four crops from the project are considered minor crops they have significant differences in terms of their situation in the studied places. For instance, the two crops considered for non-processed food (i.e., taro and sweet potatoes) are well known in the countries of study by both producers and consumers. However, the demand of taro for food in Cyprus is stagnated (both domestic and abroad). In contrast, the demand for sweet potatoes is rising domestically (e.g., in France where there is growing interest due to its nutritional characteristics). Although the domestic demand for sweet potatoes in Portugal and Greece is stable (i.e., not growing), these countries' producers benefit of an increasing foreign demand raising their exports.

It is important to note that in the case of sweet potatoes, ROTATES indicates organics as the production practice. Whilst the European Union is interested in expanding the organic supply, it needs to be done in parallel with consumers interest in organic product. The evidence about consumers interest on organic products is mixed (pointing out on the heterogeneity on consumers' preferences) and depends on factors such as prices and consumers' views about aspects such as nutrition or environment.

As regards processed products such as pasta from MRTs and yam bread an analysis of consumers preferences as their uptake will depend on factors such as their views of food safety, nutrition as well as flavours.

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